

An Overview of the Math behind the working of Recommendation Systems

Dr. Aarti Karande^a, Prof. Sakina Salmani^b

^a CSE Dept, Sardar Patel Institute of Technology, Andheri (W.), Mumbai400058 India

^b CSE Dept, Sardar Patel Institute of Technology, Andheri (W.), Mumbai400058 India

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

The way recommendation systems are made allows them to learn about the user and then match the user with recommendations based on their preferences or areas of interest. The operation of these recommendation systems involves numerous mathematical calculations in addition to the gathering of user data. The recommendation system's mathematical models guide the execution of these operations. In order to provide the user with appropriate recommendations, these models are utilised to create prediction ratings, also known as prediction scores. In their operations, these mathematical models take the mean average values into account. But there are drawbacks to using the mean average numbers as well. In order to increase the accuracy of prediction ratings or prediction scores and, consequently, the accuracy of the recommendation system, this study suggests using a median-based strategy while performing these mathematical processes.

Keywords: *Recommendation system, Mathematical Models.*

I. Introduction

Recommendation systems are systems which predict the most likely things that the user might be interested in. These systems work in such a way that at first relevant data about the user is collected. After that, this data is then filtered out keeping only the necessary data that will be used for providing recommendations. This data is then used for mind-mapping of that particular user. After mind-mapping is done, mathematical models are used to calculate prediction score. This calculated prediction score is the key factor in deciding which recommendations are to be recommended to the user. Recommendations with higher prediction score are shown first and then the pattern follows a descending order of the prediction score. Further, the literature review provides a brief explanation of various mathematical models used in the study of this paper.

II. Literature Review

A. Use of formula in Recommendation Systems:

Recommender systems collect the necessary data about the user and then create a mind map of that respective user. Based on the obtained information and mind maps recommendation systems use mathematical models for calculating the prediction rating or prediction score of a recommendation for the user. To calculate this prediction rating or prediction score in the recommendation systems mathematical models are used which comprise of formula/e and mathematical operation. The obtained rating or score is then

used by the recommendation system to predict the accurate and satisfactory recommendations to the user. There are various types and approaches for designing the architecture of recommendation systems. These different recommendation systems have different mathematical models which are used for calculating the prediction rating or prediction score. The prediction rating or prediction score plays an important role as it is one of the main deciding factors for providing accurate recommendations to the user.

B. *Mathematical Model*

The use of mathematical models in recommendation systems is important as the accuracy of the mathematical model is the key factor in deciding accurate and satisfactory recommendations. The mathematical models calculate the prediction rating or prediction score, based on which the recommendation system decides which recommendations are to be recommended. Every mathematical model has their own unique way of calculating the prediction rating or prediction score. The collected user data is computed to give the prediction rating or prediction score using one or more mathematical operations. The number of mathematical operations depends upon the approach of the mathematical model.

1. Prediction Rating Formula for Adaptive Recommendation System:

Paper [1] presents a hybrid recommender system which combines collaborative filtering technique and knowledge-based approach. This architecture uses these two techniques flexibly to provide best possible recommendations to the user. The architecture is designed in such a way that it selects either collaborative or knowledge-based filtering flexibly for service. This flexibility of a recommendation system enables the system to be adaptive in nature, which means that it can be used to cater multiple domains. The formula used for obtaining the prediction ratings is also adaptive in nature and can be used in different domains without compromising on accuracy. A drawback or challenge of this architecture is that the computational cost as well as the search cost keeps on increasing. Though this can be solutionalized by multithreading.[6] The computation on small lightweight process known as threads can be done beforehand while the user is interacting. Also partitioning of the database can be done in such a way that the database knows where to search the relevant content rather than searching the entire database. Another improvement in this approach can be made according to paper[7] where a technique called “composite archetype” can be used to help the database with information of legacy transaction data which can help to provide good recommendations to the user. Also, another technique known as “objective archetypes” provides recommendations using only categorical information.

Prediction Rating formula for Adaptive Recommendation System

$$U_x = \bar{U} + \frac{\sum_{J \in \text{Raters of } x} (J_x - \bar{J}) R_{UJ}}{\sum_{J \in \text{Raters of } x} |R_{UJ}|}$$

Equation 1. Prediction Rating Formula for Adaptive

U_x -> Rating to be predicted for user U on item x.

\bar{U} ->Mean ratings of user U.

J_x -> Rating of user J for item x.

\bar{J} ->Mean ratings.

R_{UJ} -> Similarity score.

Case Study: The model is a hybrid recommender system. Hybrid recommendation systems provide more accuracy in terms of the recommendations as two filtering techniques are combined together, collaborative filtering and knowledge-based filtering i.e. content-based filtering. The short-comings of one filtering technique is masked by the other filtering technique and vice-versa. This mathematical model is like a canvas and can be used in different domains. It provides a universal mathematical model which provides accurate recommendations.

2. Prediction Rating Formula for Collaborative Filtering:

Paper [2] proposes a similarity measure named OS which is an abbreviation of Our developed Similarity. It is used in collaborative filtering-based recommendation system. Experiments were conducted using three benchmark datasets and OS showed very competitive results as compared to Cosine Similarity (COS). Future work includes more investigation and testing of OS.

Prediction Rating Formula for Collaborative Filtering:

$$\hat{r}_{ui} = \bar{r} + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^k S_{uk} \cdot (r_{ki} - \bar{r}_k)}{\sum_{k=1}^k S_{uk}}$$

- r_{ui} ->Prediction Rating.
- \bar{r} ->Average rating of user.
- S_{uk} ->Similarity measure of user u and user's kth neighbor.
- k -> Size of the neighborhood user.
- r_{ki} ->Rating value of user k to item i.

Equation 2. Prediction Rating Formula for Collaborative Filtering based Recommendation Systems.

Case Study: The mathematical model uses collaborative filtering technique for recommendations. The filtration of the necessary data is done by the interest of the similar user having similar interests. This similarity measure is then used for providing recommendations. The proposed mathematical model is tested using different benchmark datasets. The outcome of this testing showed that the model is competitively accurate and will be tested further to know till what extent the proposed model can be used effectively maintaining accuracy of the recommendations. The mathematical model for OS comprises of two parts. The first part is responsible in taking account of similar rated items. The second part uses the similarity expression for all items rated by two similar users. The calculation

of the first part of the mathematical model is done by using the proposed mathematical formula which calculates the percentage of ratings which are uncommon. The calculation of the second part of the mathematical model is done by using the proposed mathematical formula called Absolute Difference of Ratings (ADF). The final formula is calculated by combining the first and the second part.

3. Prediction Rating Formula for Hybrid Recommender System using Dynamic weights:

A different approach to weighted hybridization is main focus of paper [3]. In place of fixed weights for the combinations, dynamic weight is used. Effectiveness is shown in the error statistics, as it boosts the performance of the recommendation system and also minimizes the problem of cold start.

Prediction Rating Formula for Hybrid Recommender System using Dynamic weights:

$$pred(a, p) = \bar{r}_a + \frac{\sum_{b \in N} sim(a, b) \cdot (r_{b,p} - \bar{r}_b)}{\sqrt{\sum_{b \in N} sim(a, b)}}$$

$$sim(a, b) = \frac{\sum_{p \in P} (r_{a,p} - \bar{r}_a) (r_{b,p} - \bar{r}_b)}{\sqrt{\sum_{p \in P} (r_{a,p} - \bar{r}_a)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{p \in P} (r_{b,p} - \bar{r}_b)^2}}$$

Equation 3. Prediction Rating Formula for Hybrid Recommendation Systems with Dynamic Weights.

N -> Number of neighbors.

a -> Active learner.

p -> Rating prediction of learning material.

$pred(a, p)$ -> Rating prediction of learner a.

$r_{b,p}$ -> Rating of learner b.

\bar{r}_a -> Average ratings of active learners.

\bar{r}_b -> Average ratings of learner b.

$sim(a, b)$ -> Similarity between a and b.

Case Study: The proposed mathematical model is used in a hybrid recommendation system. It is used for providing recommendations for learning materials amongst the active users. The main aim was to propose a powerful combination of content-based filtering technique and collaborative filtering technique. The public dataset named MovieLens in which the mathematical model was tested showed that the proposed system has less errors, which means that the proposed mathematical model has better accuracy. Future work comprises of accumulating more user experience to analyze how well the designed hybrid recommendation system works and second is the security issue that is the integration of private information with public information as discussed in paper [8]. Also, besides this, paper [9] highlights that the future recommendation system models should be designed in such a way that the accuracy of the predictions is maintained even in presence of noisy data or cases of fake user profiles. The proposed mathematical model starts with Preliminaries where consistent mathematical notations

are used for different elements of the recommendation system. Then Collaborative Filtering technique is used for calculation the prediction ratings. After the calculation of prediction ratings using collaborative filtering technique, the prediction ratings are again calculated but this time using Content-based Filtering technique. After separately calculating the prediction ratings from different techniques. The final Prediction Rating is calculated using the proposed mathematical model of the Dynamic Weighted Hybrid Recommendation System.

4. Prediction Rating Formula overcoming effective missing prediction:

Paper [4] presents a movie recommendation system named Moreopt. It uses collaborative filtering technique and aims to overcome data sparsity problem, increase the density and maximize the accuracy. Data sparsity problem is overcome by using missing prediction and collaborative filtering techniques. For prediction process both filtering techniques are used together to provide best possible recommendations. The proposed movie recommender system uses content weights for improving item similarity.

Prediction Rating Formula overcoming effective missing prediction:

$$\text{pred}(m) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 P[m, m_i] \cdot ar_i}{\sum_{i=1}^2 ar_i}$$

where,

$$P_{\text{item}}[m, m_j] = \frac{\sum_{u=1}^u (R_{u, m_i} - R_{\bar{m}_i})(R_{u, m_j} - R_{\bar{m}_j})}{\sqrt{\sum_{u=1}^u (R_{u, m_i} - R_{\bar{m}_i})^2 + \sum_{u=1}^u (R_{u, m_j} - R_{\bar{m}_j})^2}}$$

Equation 4. Prediction Rating Formula overcoming Effective Missing Prediction.

$\text{pred}(m)$ ->Rating prediction.

Case Study: The collaborative-filtering based movie recommendation system proposes a mathematical model used for providing recommendations based on interest of similar users. In this proposed model, paper [10] explains that data sparsity and scalability have considerable dependency on other users. So, to tackle this dependency the system aims to overcome this very data sparsity. The prediction for missing data is explained in paper [11] which proves to be a solution when it comes to the problem of data sparsity. The experimental tests on dataset shows that Moreopt Movie recommender system trumps the traditional filtering techniques. The variables of the proposed mathematical model for Moreopt include Set and indices, Parameters, Decision variables and the mathematical model that is the mathematical formula. The mathematical model then computes the Missing Rating Prediction. This calculation is needed because of the drawback of data sparsity in the recommendation system model. Once all the required mathematical operations are carried out, the final rating prediction is done using the proposed formula

5. Rating Prediction Formula for Hydra - a Hybrid Recommendation System Model:

Paper [5] presents a hybrid recommender system named Hydra. It combines collaborative and content-based filtering technique to form a unified model. For the minimization of runtime of the proposed recommender system, the hybrid model was

factorized via singular value decomposition (SVD). In the conducted experiments, the proposed system uses the proposed algorithm. Result shows competitive overall performance.

Rating Prediction for Hydra Hybrid Recommendation System Model:

$$\hat{r}_{ui} = [VS^{1/2}]_u \cdot [S^{1/2} \cdot W^T]_i$$

$$\hat{r}_{ui} = \frac{\sum_{j \in \text{rated items}(u)} S_{ij} \cdot r_{uj}}{\sum_{j \in \text{rated items}(u)} |S_{ij}|}$$

Equation 5. Prediction Rating Formula for Hydra Hybrid Recommendation System Model.

\hat{r}_{ui} -> Prediction rating of user u to item i.

\bar{r}_u -> Overall rating of user u. V □ Singular vectors (Left). S □ Singular Values.

W-> Singular vectors (Right).

S_{ij} -> Cosine Similarity.

Case Study: The hybrid approach is made in such a way that the content information and the rating data is combined to form a unified model. By doing this, there were less parameters to deal with and which lead to more reasonable prediction results to the user. The mathematical model of Hydra comprises of multiple mathematical operations. The operation starts with Data Normalization which does includes Subtractive Normalization followed by Multiplicative Normalization. After Data Normalization, the original rating matrix along with retrieved user matrix and item feature matrix combine to form a unified model which is for Feature Combination. After the Feature Combination of the matrices, Matrix Factorization is done to retrieve latent relation among the items of the data set and also to lessen the item space. Once the Matrix Factorization is done, the generated matrices are used in the proposed mathematical formulas to obtain the rating prediction or the prediction score. The proposed unified mathematical model also reduces the runtime of the hybrid recommender system.

Paper [12] states that more research and development is required in this domain as there is a lot of room for improvement. Various limiting factors discussed in paper [12] suggest an option of extensions for improving recommendation capabilities. These extensions would be designed to provide flexible and less intrusive recommendation process. Paper [13] study shows that a hybrid recommendation system is like combining two components of different strengths. The shortcomings of one filtering technique are overcome using the strength of the other filtering technique.

Comparison of the Mathematical Models of different Recommendation Systems:

S no	Name	Drawbacks	Realtime Usage Example
1.	Adaptive Hybrid Recommender System.[1]	High computational and search cost of user's increasing preference	The recommendation system model is used in e-commerce domain. It uses collaborative and knowledge-based filtering technique. The

		database.[1]	model is highly adaptable in any e-commerce space. The flexibility of this model to effectively choose collaborative or knowledge-based technique also enables it to be used in many domains.[1]
2.	Similarity measure OS. (Our Developed Similarity) [2]	The complexity of the formula increases the calculation time. Rating value is ignored.[2]	The collaborative filtering-based recommendation system model uses the proposed similarity measure called OS (Our Developed Similarity) for providing recommendations. This mathematical model is used in multiple domains dealing with large data.[2]
3.	Recommendation System for Learning Material Domain.[3]	Sparser the dataset, worse the performance. [3]	This recommendation model is used in the domain of education. It is used to provide the learners with the recommendations of learning materials. The model uses a hybrid approach combining of collaborative and content-based filtering technique.[3]
4.	Moreopt: Web-based Movie Recommender System.[4]	Data sparsity and scalability and the dependency on human ratings.[4]	Moreopt recommendation model is used for web-based movie recommender system. It makes use of collaborative filtering technique. It is used in the domain of movie recommendations. This model can be modified and used in multiple domains which uses collaborative filtering techniques.[4]
5.	Hydra: Hybrid Recommender system.[5]	Accuracy depends upon employed similarity measure.[5]	Hydra is a hybrid recommendation system model is currently being used for recommending movies. High efficiency and accuracy of this model makes it very useful different domains which use hybrid recommendation systems.[5]

III. Observations:

Every recommendation system tries to maximize their accuracy by gathering information about the user, making a mind map of the user, calculating the prediction rating or the prediction score using different mathematical models and then providing the user with the recommendations. If any one of the steps incur any discrepancies, inconsistencies or inaccuracies, recommendation system's accuracy gets compromised. One of the most important parts in the recommendation process is the calculation of the prediction rating or prediction score. If the recommendation system is not able to calculate accurate prediction rating or prediction score then the recommendation system is considered as less accurate. In the above five mathematical models studied in the paper for various recommendation systems using different techniques, one thing is common that is all the mathematical models consider the mean average value for the user prediction ratings as well as for the mind mapping. Though using the mean average value in the mathematical models for the recommendation system has proved to provide high accuracy recommendations. There is always a room for improvement. This is

where mathematical models should consider using the median value in place of the mean average value for calculation of the prediction ratings or the prediction score.

The advantage of using median is that, that it is not affected by extreme values. A median value can be defined as the middle value that separates the data sample into two halves and provides a center point of the data sample. So even if the data for computing the mathematical model has extreme values, then it won't lead to any major discrepancies or inconsistencies while calculating the prediction rating or prediction score. This will enable the recommendation system to be more accurate thereby providing more accurate and relevant recommendations to the users.

The same is not the case when mean average value is taken. The mean average value will basically take the average of the data. So, if the data has two extreme values, then the mean average would turn out to be the value in between the extremes which would be nor here nor there. This then results into inaccuracies while calculating prediction ratings or prediction score. Such inaccuracies make the recommendation systems provide recommendations which are far from accurate. This then coins the recommendation system to be less accurate.

Hence, this paper proposes a median-based approach to these mathematical models which proposes to provide much more accurate prediction ratings or prediction scores thereby making the recommendation system more accurate. More future work is to be done in terms of testing of the proposed median-based approach.

IV. Conclusion:

In the Recommendation Systems, when calculating the prediction ratings or prediction scores, mathematical models use the mean average value. Taking the mean average value has its cons. If the collected user data is occurred with extreme values, then the mean would change leading to discrepancies in the calculation of the prediction ratings. So, to eliminate this problem, taking the median value should be considered in place of the mean average value. This approach would enable the recommendation systems to provide more accurate recommendations. The future work of this paper comprises of the testing of the proposed median-based approach in the mathematical models of recommendation systems.

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